

تفعيل تكنولوجيا التعليم
Activating EdTech

Activating Educational Technology Sprint 1 Report

January 21-24, 2019, Amman

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Information about the Activating EdTech and our outputs can be found at <http://tiny.cc/ActivatingEdTech>.

Our outputs are archived here <https://zenodo.org/communities/aet/>.

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Project Overview

Activating Edtech aims to develop working habits and processes for the incorporation of evidence into Edtech related decision making at all levels of the Jordanian Ministry of Education. The project aims to instil the principles of collaboration, iteration and the incorporation of research by emulating these principles itself. The project, therefore, deliberately avoids a top-down and rigid approach in favour of a more communal and flexible one. As a result, the project's interim outputs and schedule are in constant flux, however, while still ensuring productivity and quality and with a clear final project output in mind.

The project is set up around 3 Sprints, defined as being intense periods of work with the Activating Edtech Team. The Team is made up of various stakeholders from within and without the MoE. During these sprints, the Team discusses and produces outputs, and agrees upon the work to be done before and during the next sprint.

Sprint Overview

The first sprint took place from January 21-24th 2019 and gathered 20 Ministry and non-Ministry stakeholders (hereafter referred to as 'the Edtech Team') to explore how to use evidence to inform decision making in EdTech. The sprint emulated the adaptive management approach it is aiming to highlight the value of to the MoE. This approach used by the consultants is different from the traditional consulting approach that many have become used to; whereby an external consultant comes with the suggested "solutions" and presents them for discussion. The approach here is deliberately designed to create a learning journey towards identifying the needed "solutions", which parties buy into by being part of that journey itself.

Sprint Goals

Goals	Status
<ul style="list-style-type: none">Form Edtech Team and set the pace for upcoming weeks	Achieved - see Output 1
<ul style="list-style-type: none">Explore the use of global evidence on Edtech	Achieved - see Output 1
<ul style="list-style-type: none">Plan for the next Sprint and determine key next steps	Achieved - Scheduled for the 17th - 21st of February 2019 - see Output 3

Outputs of Sprint 1

Output 1: The Activating Edtech Team was created and guided through an evidence-informed learning journey

- The Edtech Team reviewed the literature on the use of ICT in the classroom and teacher professional development programs and analyzed it with respect to Jordan's education system. These discussions came out with relevant findings and some key questions, including:
 - **Tech Use:**
 - How does digital behaviour at the MoE level affect digital behaviour at the classroom level? What is the link between administrative behaviour and pedagogical behaviour?
 - Technology needs to feed into and support the pedagogical and administrative tasks the teacher is expected to perform.
 - How can we evaluate tech use in class?
 - How can we reevaluate our view of tech infrastructure and utilise the technology that already exists both in school and at home?
 - How do we ensure safety and security in tech use?
 - **Teacher Professional Development (TPD):**
 - TPD programs need to be nimble to accommodate the different environments in which the teachers work. School-based TPD programs, therefore, have the advantage.

- Do we have a clear sense of teacher's willingness toward and view of professional development?
- **Stakeholder Management:**
 - How do we manage the engagement of parents in their children's learning?
- **Curriculum:**
 - The curriculum is not the same as the textbook, just as the enacted curriculum is not the same as the intended curriculum.

Output 2: A general consensus among the Activating Edtech Team that the previous draft of the National ICT in Education Strategy needs significant improvement and is not viable in its current form, and that an alternative strategy needs to be drafted.

- The Edtech Team reviewed the previous draft of the National ICT in Education Strategy against the evidence they had reviewed and comparable Edtech strategies. This exercise culminated in a number of recommendations and next steps, which were then prioritized and crystalized into the four working groups on the next day. Some of the recommendations included:
 - Reviewing previous Edtech interventions
 - Setting indicators for evaluating Edtech interventions
 - Clarifying the vision for Edtech
 - Aligning the ICT strategy with the Ministry's Education Strategic Plan
 - Exploring the use of Open Educational Resources

ربط الرؤية
بالعصر الرقمي
بدلاً من انفصال المفردة

الاستفادة من الصحافة

توفر حلول تكنولوجية تناسب النظريات التعليمية

التربية لمصنعة في الوزارة
الربط بينه وبين الوزارة / مدير إلكتروني

نماذج آتية للمصنعة لإبراهيم
تدريسي (KAS)

الاستفادة من مصادر الرقمية
المتنوعة + ومحتوى كذا في منها

مجموعة (1)
٢٠١٦/٢٢

Connecting
ICT strategy with

تقديم برنامج
لدرعم
تقبل التغيير
دمج برامج تعليمية التلاميذ
ومستوى التكنولوجية التلاميذ

تقبل التكنولوجيا والابتكار والابتعا عند التعليم
من خلال EP وخلق واستراتيجيات (الاجتهاد، المعرفة،
وقاية التلاميذ من التكنولوجيات) (Innovation
Hub)

تقبل التكنولوجيا
تقبل التغيير
دمج برامج تعليمية التلاميذ
ومستوى التكنولوجية التلاميذ

Doing Development
in a digital World
(Page 4)

التعاون
مع
القطاعات
التي
تتعلق
بها

بلد الإمارات

Output 3: Four Edtech Working Groups set up to take forward key aspects of work over the next three weeks

- Toward the end of the sprint workshop, the Activating Edtech Team formed 4 Working Groups (WG) to explore different elements of EdTech:
 - **WG 1:** ICT in the Classroom
What *should* ICT use in the classroom look like? What does it currently look like? How does the curriculum deal with the question of technology?
 - **WG 2:** Teacher Professional Development
What should a successful TPD model include? What role can technology play in this model?
 - **WG 3:** Systems Strengthening
What systems within the Ministry need to be strengthened? In what way? How can technology be used to support these systems? This group will also explore the current technological systems, such as the OpenEMIS, and their use.
 - **WG 4:** Indicators and Previous Projects:
This group will discuss what indicators should be in place to determine if an Edtech initiative should be adopted, and will then test these indicators against previous Edtech projects taken on by the Ministry.
- The 4 Working Groups are meeting weekly over the course of the three weeks in the lead up to the next sprint.
- During the final session, the Team developed a Working Groups Code of Conduct, plan and objectives for the next 3 weeks. During the course of the three weeks, the teams will explore the literature on their respective areas with regards to the MoE's Education Strategic Plan.
 - By the start of the next sprint, each group will have produced a 2-page document and a presentation on their findings. The findings shall serve as the initial principles that will guide the development of the Strategy and Roadmap.

Next steps

- The 4 Working Groups will be meeting weekly and will each develop a 2-page document in preparation for Sprint 2.
- Sprint 2 will be taking place 17th- 21st February, and will aim to:
 - Consolidate the findings of the working groups
 - Translate the findings into principles for Edtech work moving forward
 - Determine gaps in knowledge that need to be filled
 - Perform a stakeholder mapping analysis
 - Explore models of student-centred teaching and learning
 - Explore the concept of results-based management and the use of indicators